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Thin Layer Chromatographic Studies with Some Carbazoles : Hydrochloric Acid—A Convenient Spray Reagent for Carbazole Alkaloids

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CONCENTRATED hydrochloric acid has been found to be a good spray reagent for detection of carbazole alkaloids.

Thin layer chromatographic (tlc) methods have been found to be most suitable for detection and identification of minute amount of carbazoles from a given mixture¹. In each instance, the spots on the developed chromatograms were detected by means of their fluorescence under chromatolite or by the colour developed after spraying the chromatogram with picric acid. Later, we reported DDQ (2 : 3-dichloro-5, 6-dicyano benzoquinone) as a spray reagent with different carbazoles as substrates². The immediate blue to green coloration developed by spraying the spots proved to be convenient for detection of carbazoles. It was also proved to be more sensitive (0.1 μg) than picric acid (10.00 μg). However, DDQ is a quite toxic reagent.

In search for a better spray reagent for carbazole alkaloids, we noticed that non-phenolic carbazoles in contamination with phenolic ones give colour test (blue, violet, green spots) when sprayed with FeCl_3 solution. The characteristic colour reaction was also observed when sprayed with SbCl_5 solution.

The general behaviour could be explained by the fact that under experimental conditions metal chlorides could be considered to undergo hydrolysis as follows :

The resulting hydrochloric acids gave the colour reaction. Studies of the optical properties of the blue solid (also other coloured spots) in the visible

TABLE 1—COLOUR DEVELOPED AFTER SPRAYING THE CHROMATOGRAMS WITH CONC. HCl, WITH 5% FeCl_3 SOLUTION AND 10% SbCl_5 SOLUTION RESPECTIVELY

Compounds	Sources	Colour developed with			R _f
		Conc. HCl	5% FeCl_3	10% SbCl_5	
1. Carbazole	Fluka (Buchs, Switzerland)	Bluish violet	Bluish violet	Bluish violet	0.9
2. 3-methyl carbazole	<i>Clausena heptaphylla</i> Wt. and Arn.	Blue	Bluish green	Pinkish violet	0.8
3. Glycozoline	<i>Glycosmis pen'aphylla</i> Retz. D. C.	Blue	Blue	Blue	0.69
4. Glycozolidine					0.51
5. Murrayanine	<i>Murraya koenigii</i> Spreng.	Very faint blue on prolonged heating	Very faint blue on prolonged heating	Pale blue	0.35
6. Mukoic acid	"	Faint blue on heating	Faint blue on prolonged heating	"	0.25
7. Mukonine	"	"	"	"	0.36
8. Mukonidine	"	Blue on prolonged heating	Greenish blue	Blue	0.2
9. Girinimbine	"	Pink	Ash blue	Pinkish violet	0.76
10. Koenimbine	<i>Murraya koenigii</i> Spreng.	Pinkish violet	Ash blue	Pinkish violet	0.65
11. Heptazolidine	"	"	"	"	0.74
12. Koenidine	"	"	Greenish blue	"	0.25
13. Murrayacine	"	Blue on prolonged heating	Pale blue	—	0.35
14. Murrayazolidine	"	Bluish	Deep blue	Blue	0.39
15. Mahanimbine	"	Pink (dull)	Greenish blue	Bluish violet	0.93
16. N-Acetyl carbazole	Prepared in laboratory	No colour developed	No colour	No colour	—

region ($\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 550, 390) demonstrate the formation of molecular complex of the substrate with HCl of donor-acceptor type during heating³.

We were, therefore, interested to examine the behaviour of FeCl_3 , SbCl_5 and conc. HCl as spray reagents for detecting carbazole alkaloids. In all cases, the results were found to be similar i.e., the coloured spots were detected (blue, violet, green) on heating the developed chromatograms (either slowly or strongly). The coloured spots could be detected in a minimum concentration of 1 to 4 μg of carbazole or carbazole derivatives.

Experimental

Materials and Methods :

A thin layer spread on glass plate of dimension 10 cm \times 20 cm using silica-gel G as the absorbent was prepared. The chromatogram was developed in a solvent system of benzene and chloroform (1 : 1) by usual technique. The carbazole alkaloids examined, were isolated in our laboratory, from the plant sources *Murraya koenigii* Spreng., *Clausena heptaphylla* Wt. and Arn. and *Glycosmis pentaphylla* Retz. D.C. After the development of chromatogram, the spots were detected by spraying first with conc. HCl. On heating the plate at 90°, formation of colour on each of the spots was observed. The coloured spots of different compounds (with R_f) are given in the Table 1. The same experiment was repeated successively using FeCl_3 and SbCl_5 as spray reagent and the results are also shown in the same Table 1. The coloured spots could be detected at a minimum concentration of 1 μg of carbazoles in many cases.

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Synthesis of Some New 1-(Substituted Sulphamidophenyl)-2-Methyl/Aryl-4-(Substituted Benzylidene)-5-Imidazolones

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TIWARI and Satsangi¹ have reported that substituted-5-oxazolinones reacted with primary amines in pyridine to give the corresponding 5-imidazolone. Very recently Srivastava *et al*² have reported a new series of biologically active analogues of 5-imidazolone by fusing equimolar amounts of substituted-5-oxazolinones and heterocyclic primary amines at 140°.

In the present investigation various 2-Methyl/Aryl-4-(substituted benzylidene)-5-oxazolinones(I) obtained by the condensation of acetyl/substituted benzoyl glycine with substituted benzaldehydes, on interaction with various sulphonamides(II) in dry pyridine, furnished 2-Methyl/Aryl-4-(substituted benzylidene)-5-imidazolone(III). The steps involved in their synthesis are shown in chart I.

Chart I

Comparison of I.R. spectra of III with that of I indicated the absence of characteristic absorption band at 1775 cm^{-1} position assigned for carbonyl absorption of a α -lactone and appearance of bands due to carbon at 1690-1670 cm^{-1} and bands in the vicinity of 1380 cm^{-1} which is characteristic of sulphonamide group. The PMR spectrum (DMSO-d_6) of III_a (chemical shifts in δ values) showed signals at 7.24-7.58 (m, 9H, Ar-H), 7.6-8.5 (m, 4H of pyridine ring), 2.25 (s, 3H, CH_3), 7.13 (s, 1H - CH=) and 9.0 (s, 1H, NH).

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The compounds were routinely checked for their homogeneity